

STRENGTH OF ADHESIVELY BONDED COMPOSITE TUBULAR LAP JOINTS

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SUMMARY: An experimental investigation is presented to show effect of the sleeve geometry and material on the strength of adhesively bonded tube-in-sleeve joints. Both mild steel and carbon fibre composite material were used to manufacture the sleeves. FM300 film adhesive was used for all specimens. The influences of the sleeve length, sleeve thickness and the gap distance between the two tubes were investigated. Test results showed that (a) specimens with long and thin sleeves seemed to have higher failure loads and to be more flexible, (b) specimens with thick sleeves tended to have lower failure loads than those with thin sleeves, and (c) specimens with composite sleeves appeared to have lower failure loads and less flexibility than those with metal sleeves.

KEYWORDS: tube-in-sleeve, adhesively bonded, static strength, stresses, finite element analysis

INTRODUCTION

Metal and composite tubes have been widely used in many industrial sectors, for example, pipelines and tension legs in the offshore oil exploitation engineering. Joining of these tubes becomes critical in the design stage for an efficient load-carrying structure. Adhesively bonding is one of the typical tubular joining configurations, and it comprises two tubes of different diameters joined by applying a thin layer of adhesive. Similar to adhesively bonded lap joints, adhesive layer is the load transfer medium between the two tubes for adhesively bonded tubular lap joints. Research works have been done for adhesive-bonded tubular joints subjected to axial loads and/or pure torques.

Lubkin and Reissner [1] investigated the distribution of stress in the adhesive lap joints between thin circular cylindrical tubes which are subjected to axially distributed loads. For these tubular joints subjected to torsional loads, Volkersen [2] gave a closed form solution for the shear stress in the adhesive layer. Alwar and Nagaraja [3] considered the adhesive as a viscoelastic material and found the stress distribution in the adhesive layer for an adhesively bonded tubular joint in tension. Shi and Cheng [4] presented an analytical analysis of adhesive-bonded cylindrical lap joints subjected to an axial load.

Adams and Peppiatt [5] analysed the stresses in adhesive bonded tubular lap joints subjected to axial and torsion loads, using axi-symmetric quadratic isoparametric finite elements. In the axial loading case, the stress concentrations arose by three mechanisms: differential straining, bending introduced by the non-co-linearity of the overlapping tubes and end effects.

Ikegami et al [6] examined the method of tapering the adhesive coupling at the boundary of the cylinder joint (fillet) as compared to a straight edge cylinder coupling at the boundary of the lap joint. Matsui [7] studied the size effects on the average ultimate shear stress of an adhesively bonded rectangular and tubular lap joint, measured by an applied ultimate load required to produce; cohesive failure in the adherends, interfacial failure, cohesive failure in the adhesive layers or adhesive failure. As well as this, the effects of geometric size and mechanical properties of both the adherend and adhesive were also considered.

Chon [8] analysed composite tubular lap joint in torsion and developed a closed form solution for the stress distribution. More comprehensive viscoelastic analyses of adhesive bonded tubular joints under torsion were given by Medri [9] and Zhou and Rao [10].

In this investigation, simple tensile tests were carried out for adhesively bonded composite tubes-in-metal sleeve joints and composite tube-in-composite sleeve joints. The ultimate failure loads and the axial extension were measured for the joints with different sleeve lengths, sleeve thicknesses and different gap distances. The effects of these geometric parameters were identified and discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Specimen Preparation

Figure 1 depicts a typical composite tube-in-sleeve joint which comprises two composite tubes joined together by bonding the two half sleeves. Composite tubes were manufactured by rolling up a T300/934 plain weave prepreg sheet on an appropriately chosen cylindrical mandrel, and then cured in an autoclave following the manufacturer's recommended process. Care needs to be taken to maintain an appropriate tension in the prepreg sheet in the tube rolling process. The sleeves were either made of mild steel or from the same composite plain weave. The nominal thickness of T300/934 plain weave is 0.25 mm. Four plies were carefully rolled up to form a composite tube that has a wall thickness of 1 mm. Film adhesive FM300-M was used to secondarily bond the tubes and the sleeves. The nominal thickness of the adhesive layer was 0.1 mm.

All specimens have the same inner diameter of 31 mm. The composite tubes have an identical wall thickness of 1 mm. In this study, two types of materials were selected to make the sleeves, one is mild steel, and the other is the same carbon fibre reinforced composite materials. The effects of some geometrical parameters of the sleeves were investigated by changing the following parameters: the sleeve thickness t_s and the sleeve length L as shown in Fig. 1. In addition, the gap distance was also selected as a variable in order to study its effect on the failure loads of the joints. Table 1 lists the material and geometrical parameters of the sleeves for all specimens. As given in Table 1, there are three sleeve lengths (ie 20, 25 and 30 mm), three gap distances (ie, 0, 5 and 10 mm), and two sleeve thicknesses (1 and 2 mm). There are three specimens for specimen group S30-2-0, S25-2-0, S20-2-0, S30-1-5 and S30-1-10, and there is only one specimen for the remaining specimen groups.

Fig. 1: A typical configuration of an adhesively bonded tube-in-sleeve joint

Table 1: Specimen geometrical parameters for adhesively bonded composite tube-in-metal/composite sleeve joints (composite tube thickness 1 mm)

Specimen group	No. of specimen	Sleeve material	Sleeve length L (mm)	Sleeve thickness t_s (mm)	Gap distance l (mm)
S30-2-0	3	Mild steel	30	2	0
S25-2-0	3	Mild steel	25	2	0
S20-2-0	3	Mild steel	20	2	0
S30-1-0	1	Mild steel	30	1	0
S25-1-0	1	Mild steel	25	1	0
S20-1-0	1	Mild steel	20	1	0
S30-1-5	3	Mild steel	30	1	5
S30-1-10	3	Mild steel	30	1	10
C30-1-0	1	Composite	30	1	0
C25-1-0	1	Composite	25	1	0
C20-1-0	1	Composite	20	1	0

The mechanical properties for a plain weave lamina are given in Table 2. The mechanical properties of FM300-M film adhesive and mild steel are given in Table 3.

Table 2: Mechanical properties for a plain weave lamina

Longitudinal and transverse modulus E_1 and E_2 (GPa)	57.23
Modulus in the through-thickness direction E_3 (GPa)	4.80
In-plane shear modulus G_{12} (GPa)	4.48
Out-of-plane shear modulus G_{13} and G_{23} (GPa)	4.4
In-plane Poisson ratio μ_{12}	0.05
Out-of-plane Poisson ratio μ_{13} and μ_{23}	0.28

Table 3: Mechanical properties for FM300-M film adhesive and mild steel

Material	FM300-M	Mild steel
Modulus E (GPa)	2.4	200
Poisson ratio μ	0.3	0.3

Test Set-up and Procedure

All composite tube-in-sleeve joints were loaded in axial tension on an Instron machine. To ensure that premature failure doesn't occur outside the tube-in-sleeve zone, end reinforcements were designed to hold the composite tube and to apply axial loads. This was achieved by first bonding metal sleeves at the end of the composite tube and then drilling a pin-load hole through both metal sleeves and the composite tube. All specimens were tested at a room temperature by applying an axial displacement or extension at a constant rate of 0.2 mm per minute. The applied displacements and the axial forces were recorded for all specimens.

Results and Discussions

Figures 2, 3 and 4 depict the typical graphs of the applied axial forces versus the axial extensions for specimen S20-1-0, S30-1-5 and C25-1-0 respectively. As shown in Figs 2 and 4, at the initial loading stage the load and extension graphs exhibit a nonlinear behaviour, and then the applied load increases almost linearly with the axial extension until a dramatically load drop occurred. This load drop was accompanied by a big bang that represented the ultimate failure of the joint specimens. For specimen group S30-1-5, prior to the final fracture of the joint, there exists a nonlinear variation segment in which the applied load oscillated at a very small amplitude. In fact, some specimens experienced a few noticeable load drops before the tube-in-sleeve joints completely lost its load transferring capacity.

Fig. 2: Axially applied tensile force vs the axial extension for specimen S20-1-0

Careful Inspection revealed that there existed two typical failure surfaces. For the first case, adhesive was seen on the outer surfaces of the composite tubes and on the inner surfaces of the sleeves, which indicates adhesive failure. For the second case, some fibres were noticed on the inner surfaces of the metal sleeves, and this observation may suggest a delamination failure in the composite tubes. It should be pointed out that for most specimens both failure surfaces were observed at different locations for a single specimen because of the nonuniform thickness of the adhesive layer. It was noted that adhesive failure tends to take place in an area close to the joining lines of the two half sleeves where the adhesive layer was noticed to be very thin. The contributing factors may include: geometric difference between the tube and sleeves due to manufacturing tolerances, difference in the coefficients of thermal expansion between the metal and the composite material used.

Fig. 3: Axially applied tensile force vs the axial extension for specimen S30-1-5

Fig. 4: Axially applied tensile force vs the axial extension for specimen C25-1-0

Table 4 summarises the failure loads and the failure extensions for all specimens. The standard deviations for these specimen groups with 3 specimens are also listed in Table 4 to indicate the range of the failure loads. For these specimens which have the same sleeve thickness and no gap between the two composite tubes, both the failure loads and the failure extensions become larger as the sleeve length increases from 20 mm to 30 mm. This indicates that when the sleeve length is the only varying parameter in the range of 20 mm and 30 mm, the joints with long sleeves fail at higher load and become more flexible. Figure 5 plots the measured failure loads versus the sleeve overlap length to sleeve thickness ratio $L/2t_s$. These curves present the same trends as that predicted by Lubkin and Reissner [1], namely, as the ratio $L/2t_s$ increases the failure loads increase. However, it is noted that Lubkin and Reissner [1] predicted a plateau after the ratio $L/2t_s$ becomes large enough for adhesive bonded tubular lap joints. Further test results need to be obtained to validate this predicted relationship between the failure load and the sleeve overlap length to thickness ratio. It is believed that the failure of the tube-in-sleeves joints transits from a peel dominated failure to a shear dominated failure when the ratio $L/2t_s$ increases. When the ratio $L/2t_s$ is low, increase in its value can reduce the peel stress in the adhesive layer and thus leads to the rising failure loads.

Table 4: Failure loads (kN) and extensions (mm) for the bonded composite tube-in-metal/composite sleeve joints

Specimen group	Failure load	Failure elongation
S30-2-0	7.33±0.359	1.40±0.262
S25-2-0	4.75±0.030	0.75±0.126
S20-2-0	2.60±0.747	0.49±0.061
S30-1-0	25.21	3.11
S25-1-0	21.08	1.88
S20-1-0	13.91	1.54
S30-1-5	16.86±1.779	1.76±0.191
S30-1-10	20.38±6.67	1.98±0.561
C30-1-0	16.77*	2.45
C25-1-0	9.19	0.96
C20-1-0	6.84	0.79

* Premature failure at one end reinforcement

For these specimens only having different sleeve thickness, the specimens with a sleeve thickness of 1 mm tend to have much higher average failure loads and larger average extensions than those with a sleeve thickness of 2 mm, for example, specimen S30-1-0 has an average failure load of 25.21 kN which is much larger than the average failure load 7.33 kN for specimen S30-2-0.

By comparing the average failure loads and extensions for specimen S30-1-0, S30-1-5, and S30-1-10, it is noted that specimen S30-1-0 tends to be the strongest one while specimen S30-1-5 tends to be the weakest one. Increasing the gap distance from 5 mm to 10 mm does increase the failure loads slightly. However, a relative large standard deviation was noted for specimen S30-1-10 which indicates a large scatter in the failure loads.

Another interesting result worth noting is that those joints having composite sleeves tend to fail at lower failure loads and less extensions than those having metal sleeves. By comparing the material properties for the mild steel and the composite materials listed in Tables 2 and 3, it is found that the mild steel has a much higher modulus, and thus a larger membrane and bending stiffness, than the plain weave composite material. Preliminary numerical results indicate that metal sleeves produce negative peel stress in the adhesive layer when subjected to a tensile load. Another contributing factor can be the residual stress that was created during the curing process due to the difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion between the metal and composite material for these joints with metal sleeves.

Fig. 5: Measured failure loads versus the sleeve overlap length to thickness ratio $L/2t_s$.

CONCLUSIONS

An experimental investigation was carried out to study the effects of the sleeve geometry and material on the strength of adhesively bonded tube-in-sleeve joints. Two types of materials were used to make the sleeves: mild steel and carbon fibre composite mater. FM300 film adhesive was used to adhesively bonded the tubes and the sleeves for all specimens. It was shown that the composite tube-in-metal sleeves joints with long and thin sleeves tend to have higher failure loads and to be more flexible than those with short and thick sleeves. The composite tube-in-composite sleeves joints appeared to have lower failure loads and less axial flexibility than the composite tube-in-metal sleeves joints. Increasing the gap distance from 5 to 10 mm between the composite tubes seemed to yield an increase in both failure loads and axial extensions.

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